

Recent studies on the application of electrocoagulation associated with membrane filtration in the treatment of anaerobic digestion effluents

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Abstract

This research presents a bibliometric review that surveys author productivity, publication timeline, geographic distribution, and keyword frequency in articles published within the last 10 years on treatment and nutrient recovery of anaerobic digestates based on processes of electrocoagulation and membrane filtration, exploring the current applications and future opportunities of the matter. Bibliometric data analysis was performed using diverse programming tools, revealing an increase in the number of publications on the subject, primarily in India, Italy, China, Egypt, and Mexico, as well as the occurrence of main keywords such as electrocoagulation, removal, and wastewater. Multiple authors discuss these two treatment methods' efficiency, advantages, and disadvantages, concluding that integrating combined technologies is a promising area that needs further research to address existing challenges.

Keywords

Biodigester effluent; Digestate; Electrochemistry; Membrane filtration; Removal technologies; Resource recovery.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing water scarcity tends to lead modern industry and governments to turn to alternatives capable that ensure satisfactory water supply, including treated wastewater reuse in agriculture (Ibrahimi et al., 2025). The biogas fermentation process forms, among other substances, the digestate, a nutrient-rich subproduct that is commonly used in the soil as a biofertilizer. However, this effluent can contain physical, chemical, and biological contaminants such as plastic, undigestible wood, heavy metals, antibiotics, and pathogens, representing a risk to the environment and living beings, and reducing the final quality of the fertilizer. Therefore, digestate post-treatment is essential to ensure quality improvement and nutrient recovery (Duan et al., 2025).

Facing this, electrochemical processes like electrocoagulation pose as a novel alternative to enhance the properties of the effluent and recover its nutrients by applying an electric current, aiming to remove multiple contaminants (Das; Sharma; Purkait, 2022). Additionally, membrane filtration, a high-efficiency process applied for similar purposes, utilizes pressure to separate fluids and solids depending on membrane's pore size. The selective transport of substances through membrane pores plays a critical role in determining membrane performance, making pre-treatment of the feed essential to enhance the efficiency of the process. Combining electrocoagulation and membrane filtration offers a promising approach, as electrocoagulation can effectively reduce one of the primary challenges in membrane processes: fouling (Cevallos-Mendoza et al., 2022).

Thus, the main goal of this research is to conduct a bibliometric review, carrying out a survey of the productivity of authors, publication timeline, geographic distribution, and frequency of keywords in articles within the current publication scenario on the treatment of digestate from anaerobic digestion based on the processes of electrocoagulation and membrane filtration, exploring the possible applications and future opportunities of the theme.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) methodology, which enables an integrative analysis of data from a specific discourse

domain (Agyekum et al., 2024). The key research question was first defined, and the bibliographic search stage began using the Web of Science and Scopus databases.

The search used boolean operators and truncation, aiming to define the research scope better. The resultant search string was “(digestate* OR BDE OR "biodigester effluent" OR "bio digester effluent" OR "anaerobic reactor effluent" OR "anaerobic reactor effluents" OR "anaerobic digester effluent" OR "anaerobic digester effluents" OR "biogas effluent" OR "biogas effluents" OR biofertilizer* OR fertilizer* OR biodigester*) AND (electrocoagulation OR electroflocculation OR electrochemistry) AND (membrane* OR “membrane filtration” OR filtration OR ultrafiltration OR microfiltration OR nanofiltration OR “reverse osmosis” OR “filtering membrane” OR “filtering membranes”)”.

The selection criteria included only documents published in the last 10 years (2014-2024), and those expected for 2025. The search was limited to research and review articles in Portuguese, English and Spanish, excluding book chapters and notes. Any overlap identified between the two databases was also discarded, avoiding duplication. Bibliometric data analysis was performed using R Studio, Bibliometrix tool, and VOSviewer version 1.6.20. The flowchart for the PRISMA method used in this study is presented in Figure 1, resulting in 4 final relevant documents.

Figure 1. PRISMA method flowchart, where “WoS” refers to Web of Science.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data from the two databases was combined using the R Studio program. Over the past decade, the number of publications on digestate treatment and nutrient recovery using electrochemistry and membranes has gradually increased, reaching its peak in 2024. The top five contributing countries were India, Italy, China, Egypt and Mexico, with 16, 6, 5, 4 and 4 publications, respectively. Together, these countries accounted for 66.04% of the total articles published. The most prominent authors are Chaudhari P. and Prajapati A. The leading journals publishing these articles are *Desalination and Water Treatment* and *Science of the Total Environment*.

The keywords examination on the VOSviewer tool created a co-occurrence network distinguished by different colours - red, green and blue -, depending on the research trends (Figure 2). The most frequent keywords indicate an increasing focus on studies related to electrocoagulation, removal, wastewater, coagulation, pulp, recovery, adsorption, fertilizer, and aqueous solution.

Figure 2. Bibliometric study. (A) Scientific Production between 2014 and 2025; (B) Network visualization of the keywords – VOSviewer map; (C) Country scientific production; (D) Word cloud for author keywords.

Table 1 presents the 4 final selected manuscripts that most fit the theme based on the PRISMA methodology.

Table 1. Most relevant documents and their references

Title	Reference
Treatment of rice grain-based distillery effluent using hybrid electrocoagulation–microfiltration processes: performance and optimization	Dubey et al., 2022.
Electrochemical treatment of biodigester effluent of maize based starch industry	Mazumdar and Chaudhari, 2015.
Macro-nutrients recovery from liquid waste as a sustainable resource for production of recovered mineral fertilizer: Uncovering alternative options to sustain global food security cost-effectively	Sniatala et al., 2023.
A critical review on retaining antibiotics in liquid digestate: Potential risk and removal technologies	Yang et al., 2022.

Sniatala et al. (2023) critically reviewed the technical applicability of different technologies for recovering nutrients such as phosphorus, nitrogen, and potassium from various types of wastewater, including the concentrate of anaerobically digested sewage sludge and swine manure. The authors classify electrocoagulation as a cost-effective treatment method that generates coagulants in situ through electrolytic oxidation. This process combines the benefits of coagulation, flotation, and electrochemistry and achieving over 90% phosphorus removal. Further, in this study, membrane filtration is described as another highly effective and selective technology for nutrient recovery, capable of concentrating nutrients to be posteriorly reused as fertilizers. For instance, it is highlighted that ammonia can pass through a microporous membrane, and sulfuric acid can be used to recover nitrogen as ammonium sulphate. Both processes face challenges related to fouling and sludge generation which could be mitigated when the methods are integrated.

Furthermore, Dubey et al. (2022) studied the treatment of digestate from the rice grain-based distillery industry using electrocoagulation and a combination of electrocoagulation followed by microfiltration (EC-MF) in tangential flow. The digestate used exhibited high colour and chemical

oxygen demand (COD), which were removed by the EC-MF 99.9% and 98.6%, respectively. The authors also noted individual electrocoagulation achieved removal of 87% COD, while microfiltration resulted in an 80% reduction. These results indicate that the EC-MF is more effective for treating biodigester effluent than electrocoagulation or microfiltration alone.

Moreover, Mazumdar and Chaudhari (2015) also evaluated the effects of reduction COD and colour in digestate using electrocoagulation followed by filtration through a Whatman 42 filter. They utilized iron electrodes to treat wastewater from maize-based starch industry biodigester, reaching a maximum reduction in COD of 89% and colour of 97% at pH of 6.5 and a current density 99 A m^{-2} . Similarly, the substantial levels of antibiotics such as Tetracycline, Ofloxacin and Amoxicillin found in liquid digestate can be reduced with the use of bioelectrochemical systems, including microbial fuel cells (MFC) and microbial electrolysis cells (MEC) and membrane separation combined with biological treatment, i.e. membrane bioreactors (MBR) (Yang et al., 2022). These systems include membrane interception, adsorption, biodegradation, and hydrolysis. In summary, the selection of removal technologies must consider the characteristics of the effluent to ensure both efficient removal and an economically viable process.

In conclusion, integration of technologies, including electrocoagulation and membrane filtration for contaminants and pathogen removal, and nutrient recovery, represents a promising area for further research. By merging different methods, it is possible to overcome the limitations of individual technologies and enhance overall efficiency. A thorough assessment of these approaches is crucial, considering factors such as the simultaneous removal of diverse contaminants, potential interference from other pollutants, economic feasibility, and environmental sustainability. Electrocoagulation and membrane filtration have demonstrated high effectiveness in these processes, but further studies are essential to enrich the existing literature and optimize their application.

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